

EFFECT OF METACOGNITIVE SKILL ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF IX STANDARD STUDENTS IN THE SUBJECT OF ECONOMICS

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Abstract

“Let our learners’ imagination reach the pinnacle with the intent that they will never fall into the nadir of demoralization. The learners whether expert or novice should be self-motivated so that they can eternally strive towards broadening their cognitive horizons.”
(Mrs. Debaleena Roy).

One of the hallmarks of psychological and educational theories and researches on learning is the emphasis on helping students to become more knowledgeable and responsible for their own cognition. Researchers agree that growing students become aware of their own thinking as well as more knowledgeable about cognition in general. Teaching children the need and method of thinking, rethinking, regulating and monitoring of thinking is the crucial and an arduous task for the educators. In the first place, it seems impossible but with the persistent training and empathetic guidance, one can achieve the different faculty, namely metacognition. It is at all times; however, a subject of authenticity for the teachers, and the onus of establishing the notion, metacognition, lies on the coach who advocates it. In colloquial term, it is all about higher order thinking strategies to achieve advanced goals.

The present study intended to probe the effectiveness of integrated Metacognitive skill on the academic performance of IX Standards students in the Subject Economics. Integration of Metacognitive learning skill constituted of strategies like Self-Planning, self-Monitoring, and Self-Regulations along with lecture-demonstration method through Concept map, Keyword method, Method of Loci, Chunking and First letter Technique. In

this study, the experimental method was used. The design used for the study was Pre Test Post-test for the Experimental group and the control group design with the help of teacher-made test and Metacognitive Awareness Inventory (MAI), Schraw, G. & Dennison, R.S. (1994). Population consisted of IX Standard students of DG International School Thane, Maharashtra, India. The population was selected from the school by convenience sampling. 33 IX Standard students (17 for Experimental Group and 16 for Control Group) as student sample by random sampling technique. Data were obtained from samples by a teacher made pre-test and pot test and obtained data were analysed by statistical tools viz., Mean, SD, t-test, Pearson's Correlation Coefficient and effect size. From the results of the experiment, it was concluded that Metacognitive strategies are effective for IX standard students.

Keywords: *Metacognitive Skill, Academic Performance, IX Standard students.*

Introduction

Metacognition is identified in simplest terms as “thinking about one’s own thinking.” The derivation Meta means beyond, so the worded note is beyond thinking. Therefore, we can say that Metacognition talks about learners’ natural awareness of their own knowledge or information and their capability to recognize, control and work according to their own cognitive procedures. Educational events should involve students to think rationally and act. The current epoch of 21st Century Proficiencies has acknowledged metacognition as one of the life skill essential to make students ready for post-secondary education.

Definitions

John Flavell originally coined the term metacognition in the late 1970s to mean “cognition about cognitive phenomena,” or more simply “thinking about thinking” (Flavell, 1979, p. 906).

- “The knowledge and control children have over their own thinking and learning activities” (Cross & Paris, 1988, p. 131).

Thus, the main quintessence of the theory revolves around the following factors:-

Self-Variables- A person’s ability to recognize his or her own ability and inability to accomplish a task.

Functional Variables: A person’s knowledge about the quality and nature of a task or assignment. A person knows precisely the procedures to complete the particular task.

Stratagem variables: The plan of action that a person is ready to apply in an adaptable manner to complete a task is known as the stratagem variable. One should hit the Bull’s

eye to achieve the goal.

Economics is a subject that embraces all aspects of human behaviour, on the one hand, it joins psychology, but on the other hand, it joins mathematics and statistics. To accomplish an advanced level of performance in Economics stream, the student should use a well-defined or self-directed learning strategy. Strategies of metacognition will enable the students to realize their own potentialities and drawbacks to achieve goals. We can train the students of Economics to embrace metacognitive skill to excel in the field of Economics.

For example, some student is getting very poor marks in Micro Economics and if he can identify the areas, where he is lagging behind then it is easier for him to find the definite solution. Students need help to understand that different learning activities Create different expectations. **For example**, for the primary students of Economics, the new terminologies of National Income Accounting appear difficult, on the contrary, for the Junior College students; it is a simple concept to learn. They have already discovered when and why to use terminologies effectively.

Objectives of the study

- 1) To ascertain the effect of metacognitive skill on post-test scores of experimental group students in the subject Economics.
- 2) To investigate the relationship between metacognitive skill and academic performance among IX standard students of the experimental group in the subject of Economics.
- 3) To find the difference between the posttest mean scores of academic performance of control and experimental group students in the subject of Economics.
- 4) To find the difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores of academic performance of experimental group students in the subject Economics.

Hypotheses of the study

- 1) There is no significant effect of metacognitive skill on post-test scores of experimental group students in the subject Economics.
- 2) There is no significant relationship between metacognitive skill and academic performance among IX standard students of the experimental group in the subject of Economics.
- 3) There is no significant difference between the post-test mean scores of academic performance of control and experimental group students in the subject of Economics.

4) There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test mean scores of academic performance of experimental group students in the subject Economic

Methods Used in the Study: - The researchers used Pre Test Post Test Non- Equivalent Group design. It is one of the strongest and the most widely used quasi Experimental Designs.

Techniques of Data analysis

Quantitative data analysis

(Quasi-experimental Design)

The Pre-test-Post-test Non-equivalent Groups Designs

O1 X O2 O1 O3 = Pre-test

O3 C O4 O2 O4 = Post-tests

Sample- The population, was selected from the school by convenience sampling. 33 IX Standard students (17 for Experimental Group and 16 for Control Group) as student sample by random sampling technique.

Variables-

Independent Variable- Metacognitive Skill.

Dependent Variable- Academic Performance.

Operational Definition Of the terms:-

Metacognitive Skill – It could be operationally defined as the higher order thinking process of an individual that can be achieved through the meticulous planning, monitoring and regulation. It is the sum total of declarative knowledge, procedural knowledge and conditional knowledge of a person.

Academic Performance- It could be operationally defined as the central force that drives the whole machinery of the teaching-learning process and impact of different teaching methodologies, which yield a high level of achievement. It is the aggregate of all the assessment, which involves

Higher order mental operations.

The Researchers used the following strategy for the period of one month on the topic of Poverty and unemployment to train the IX standard students for developing Metacognitive skill.

Concept Map- A concept map is a type of graphic organizer which starts with a core concept and then branch out to explain how that main idea can be broken down in precise

themes. The researcher explained the students to form the concept map on the topic of poverty.

Keyword Method- In this method, a familiar word is used to associate two other words or items. The researcher explained the students to remember Poverty-line, Causes of poverty, important points of the vicious circle of poverty for forming a mental image on the concept of poverty.

Method of Loci- The word loci is the plural form of the locus which means location or place. The researcher

Trained the students to remember the long lists of poverty alleviation programmes initiated by the Indian Governments. This method is helpful to visualise items by thinking of location situated in the concept map.

Chunking- A chunk is a group of familiar stimuli stored as a single unit. The researcher trained the students to make chunks of different types of unemployment prevalent in Indian Economy. For example, rural unemployment and urban unemployment used as different chunks for successfully recalling the different types of unemployment which fall under rural and urban chunks.

First letter technique- In this technique, the researcher took the first letter of each item of employment policies of Indian Government since independence. She asked the students to apply this technique to improve their declarative knowledge.

IX Standard Students- Students enter the secondary course after passing elementary School examination.

The procedure of the present research

Table 1

Tools used	Experimental Group	Control Group
Metacognitive Awareness Inventory (MAI)	(Pre-test on MAI)	(Pre-test on MAI)
Teacher Made Performance test	(Pre-test on Performance Test)	(Pre-test Performance Test)
Treatment will be given to Experimental Groups through Instructional Modules for one month (Including Concept map, Keyword method, Method of Loci, Chunking, First letter Technique)		
Tools used	Experimental Group	Control Group
Metacognitive Awareness Inventory (MAI)	(Post-Test on MAI)	(Post-Test on MAI)
Teacher Made Performance test	(Post-Test Performance on Test)	Post-Test on Performance Test)

Table 2

Tools used in the present research- In this research study, the Metacognitive Awareness Inventory (MAI) developed by Schraw and Dennison, 1994 was used to assess the metacognitive awareness. The MAI which is a 52 item inventory is a comprehensive scale assessing various facets of metacognition, including Knowledge of Cognition and Regulation of Cognition (Schraw & Dennison, 1994). The MAI was preferred because it is easy to administer and it taps into the two-component model of metacognition, Metacognitive Knowledge and Metacognitive Regulation. The researcher used MAI to analyze relationships between metacognitive skills and academic performance of the students.

Mechanism of metacognition		
Metacognitive Knowledge	Metacognitive Regulation	Metacognitive Experience
<p>Declarative Knowledge- knowledge about oneself.</p> <p>Procedural knowledge- knowledge about how to accomplish a task.</p> <p>Conditional knowledge- Knowing particularly as when and why to make use of declarative and procedural knowledge.</p>	<p>Planning- Apposite choices, approaches and the processes for making correct decisions for realizing the goals.</p> <p>Monitoring- Describes one's awareness of understanding and task presentation.</p> <p>Evaluating- Declare to assessing the ultimate product of a task and the effectiveness at which the assignment was executed.</p>	<p>Metacognitive Experience can make use of affective, cognitive and psychomotor spheres, which can be used independently, or in collaboration of three. It consists of emotion, decision and approximation or online task-specific knowledge.</p>
Strategies to develop Metacognitive Skill among the IX Standard Students		
<p>Concept Map and Keyword method were used to develop declarative knowledge among the students.</p>	<p>Method of Loci and Chunking were introduced to the students to develop the skill of metacognitive regulation.</p>	<p>The researcher trained the students to use these methods according to the different learning situations.</p>

Table 3 Metacognitive Awareness Inventory, Schraw and Dennison, 1994 (52) Items

Knowledge of Cognition (KC)(17 items)	(KC)(17 items) Regulation of Cognition (RC) (35 items)
Declarative Knowledge (8 items) Procedural Knowledge (4 items) Conditional Knowledge (5 items)	Planning (7 items) Information management strategy (10 items) Comprehension monitoring (7 items) Debugging strategies (5 items) Evaluation (6 items)

The students of Experimental group would learn the content through the assimilation of Metacognitive learning skill constituted of strategies like Self-Planning, self-Monitoring and Self-Regulations along with lecture-demonstration method through Concept map, Keyword method, Method of Loci, Chunking and First letter Technique and solved the problems in the classroom in front of the researcher. They indulged in chat and discussion with the friends and the teacher at the time of lesson. At the same time, they would develop awareness about metacognitive strategies. Thus they developed the strategy of metacognition along with the aids of interest towards the subject of Economics. The control group, on the other hand, received the conventional lecture method on the same topic of Economics. They also solved the problems and questions and answer in the presence of the teacher. In the beginning, one pre-test was administered by the researcher and the students of the control group and experiment group took a similar test. At the end of one month, both the groups would take a test on the same topic.

Techniques of Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistics- Mean and Standard Deviation. (All variables are on the ratio scale)

The mean and standard deviation

$$\text{Mean } \bar{X} = \frac{\sum fm}{N}$$

$$\text{Standard deviation } \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fd^2}{N}}$$

Pearson’s Coefficient of Correlation

$$r = \frac{\sum (X - \bar{X})(Y - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum (X - \bar{X})^2} \sqrt{\sum (Y - \bar{Y})^2}}$$

Inferential Statistics:-

Assuming unequal variances, the t-test statistic is calculated as:

Standard Error of the difference between means (SED) = $\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_1^2}{N_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{N_2}}$

$t = \frac{(M_1 - M_2)}{\text{SED}}$

SED

Statistical significant of a Coefficient of Correlation:- $t = \frac{r\sqrt{N-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}}$

The teacher made test on academic performance – The teacher made 50 marks test on the topics Poverty and unemployment.

Table 4 Blueprint of the Question Paper from the unit

Typology/ Taxonomy of Question	MCQ/ Objective type 1 mark	Very Short Answer 2 mark	Short Answer 3 mark	Long Answer 5 mark	Marks	Percentage
Remembering (Concepts and types of poverty & unemployment)	5(1)	2(2)	1(3)	-	12	24
Understanding (Different causes of Poverty & unemployment)	4(1)	1(2)	1(3)	-	09	18
Applying (Measures to eradicate poverty and unemployment)	1(1)	1(2)	1(3)	-	06	12
Analysing (Economic reason behind poverty & unemployment)	-	-	1(3)	1(5)	08	16
Evaluating (Causes of Poverty and unemployment)	-	-	-	2(5)	10	20
Creating (Concept map On the vicious circle of poverty)	-	-	-	1(5)	05	10
	10	08	12	20	50	100

Table 5

Marks obtained by the students of Control Group and Experimental Group

Experimental Group (17 students)				Control Group (16 Students)			
Pre-test MAI	Post-test MAI	Pre-test Teacher made performance test	Post-test Teacher made performance test	Pre-test MAI	Post-test MAI	Pre-test The teacher made a performance test	Post-test The teacher made a performance test
Total Marks 52	Total Marks 52	Total Marks 50	Total Marks 50	Total Marks 52	Total Marks 52	Total Marks 50	Total Marks 50
20	46	22	50	28	32	30	33
21	39	27	48	22	23	22	29
28	47	28	49	24	24	22	26
29	38	29	47	25	26	24	27
26	46	22	49	26	20	22	29
27	42	22	47	22	25	24	33
21	42	23	47	23	25	25	32
22	44	28	48	18	25	27	30
23	40	30	46	19	22	22	34
25	38	31	45	23	33	27	38
23	38	32	45	22	30	22	35
28	39	17	47	21	36	26	38
30	40	18	45	19	30	28	36
30	39	25	46	19	20	22	30
21	43	21	47	18	28	00	03
19	42	20	49	17	21	23	24
18	45	17	50				

Table 6

Testing of Hypothesis 1. There is no significant effect of metacognitive skill on post-test scores of experimental and control group students in the subject Economics.

Name of the variables	Group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Cohen's d	Level of significance
MAI	Experimental	17	41.64	2.99	3.82	Two tailed test at the 0.05 level of significance.
MAI	Control	16	26.25	4.82		

This implies that if we see a d of 1, we know that the two groups' means differ by one standard deviation; a d of .5 tells us that the two groups' means differ by half a standard deviation; and so on. Cohen suggested that $d=0.2$ be considered a 'small' effect size, 0.5 represents a 'medium' effect size and 0.8 a 'large' effect size. This means that if two groups' means don't differ by 0.2 standard deviations or more, the difference is trivial, even if it is statistically significant. Here the effect size is more than 0.8 which means that there is a significant effect of metacognitive skill on post-test scores of experimental group and not on the control group students in the subject Economics, hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 7

Testing of Hypothesis 2. There is no significant relationship between metacognitive skill and academic performance among IX standard students of the experimental group in the subject of Economics.

Name of the variables	Group	N	Mean	Coefficient of correlation	Level of significance
MAI	Experimental	17	41.64	r = 0.79, tr = 4.92	Two tailed test at the 0.05 level of significance.
AP	Experimental	17	47.35		

(AP= Academic Performance)

With N-2 degrees of freedom, a coefficient of correlation is judged as statistically significant when the t value equals or exceeds the t critical value in the t distribution table. Here $r = 0.79$ and $N = 34$ with $N-2$, 32 degrees of freedom. The researcher used a two-tailed test at the 0.05 level with 15 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis is rejected, exceeding the t critical value of 2.04. Hence, there is a significant relationship between metacognitive skill and academic performance among IX standard students of the experimental group in the subject of Economics.

Table 8

Testing of Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between the post-test mean scores of academic performance of control and experimental group students in the subject of Economics.

The p -value is $< .00001$.

The result is significant at $p < .05$. The result of Table 8 revealed that there is a significant difference in academic performance of experimental group and control group

students in the subject Economics as t value 8.64 at 0.05 level which is higher than the actual t value i.e. 2.042 when degrees of freedom is 31, hence, the proposed hypothesis is rejected.

Table 9

Testing of Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test mean scores of academic performance of experimental group students in the subject Economics.

Name of the variables	Group	N	Mean	SD	t- ratio	df	Level of significance
AP	Experimental	17	24.23	4.77	12.56	32	Two-tailed test at the 0.05 level of significance.
AP	(pre-test)						
	Experimental	17	47.35	1.61			
	(post-test)						

(AP = academic Performance, SD = Standard Deviation, df = degrees of freedom)

The p-value is < .00001.

The result is significant at $p < .05$. The result of Table 9 revealed that there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test mean scores in academic performance of students in the subject Economics as t value 12.56 at 0.05 level which is higher than the actual t value i.e. 2.042 when degrees of freedom is 32, hence, the proposed hypothesis is rejected.

Findings of the research:-

- 1) There is an absolute significant effect of metacognitive skill on post-test scores of experimental group students in the subject of Economics.
- 2) There is a significant relationship between metacognitive skill and academic performance among IX standard students of the experimental group in the subject Economics.
- 3) There is a significant difference between the post-test mean scores of academic performance of control and experimental group students in the subject of Economics.
- 4) There is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test mean scores of academic performance of experimental group students in the subject Economics.

Educational Implications of the present research:-

1. It is possible and at the same time feasible process to develop Metacognitive skill among the students.

2. This research successfully judged the explicit metacognitive strategy awareness of the experimental and the control groups.
3. Achievement of a higher level of metacognitive regulation is possible among the secondary school children.
4. The accomplishment of metacognitive interest level and academic performance are achievable through different learning techniques.
5. Absolute metacognitive skill can be inculcated among the secondary school children.
6. Prediction of the overall enhancement of academic performance of Economics learning through metacognitive regulation, metacognitive knowledge and metacognitive skill is actually possible. The teacher should develop this life- skill to school children from the beginning of achieving higher level cognitive practices.

The conclusion-

The researcher wants the students to get into the habit of Metacognitive learning skills for creating a genre of diverse learners. Hence, the main aim is to trigger positive emotions among the learners and finally make them more and more true-to-life pupils to face the world with the hidden smiles.

References:-

- Aggarwal, J.C. & Gupta, S. (2006). Great Philosophers and Thinkers on Education. Delhi: Shipra Publications.
- Flavell, J.H. (1976). Metacognitive aspects of problem-solving. In L.B.Resick(Ed), The Nature of intelligence (pp.231-236). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Flavell, J.H. (1979). Metacognition and cognitive monitoring: A new era of cognitive developmental inquiry. American Psychologist, 34, 906-911.
- Haller, E. P., Child, D. A., & Walberg, H. J. (1988). Can comprehension be taught? A quantitative synthesis of metacognitive studies. Educational Researcher, 17(9), 5-8.
- Schneider, W. &Lockl, K. (2002). The development of metacognitive knowledge in children and adolescents. In Perfect, T. & Schwartz, B. (Eds.), Applied Metacognition. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Schraw, G. (1998). Promoting general metacognitive awareness. Instructional Science, 26(1-2), 113-125.

Schraw, G., Crippen, K. J., & Hartley, K. (2006). Promoting self-regulation in science education: Metacognition as part of a broader perspective on learning. *Research in Science Education*, 36, 111-139.

Schraw, G. & Moshman, D. (1995). Metacognitive theories. *Educational Psychology Review*, 7(4), 351-371.

References (Websites)

- www.cambridgescholars.com/download/sample/59586
- https://clio.columbia.edu/?q=metacognition&datasource=quicksearch&search_field=all_fields&search=true
- https://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/bitstream/handle/2027.42/108721/marulisl_1.pdf
- https://images.pearsonassessments.com/.../Metacognition_Literature_Review_Final.pdf
- <https://keydifferences.com/difference-between-anova-and-ancova.html#Definition>
- <https://www.learning-theories.com/metacognition-flavell.html>
- <http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/simple-search?query=metacognition>
- www.springer.com/cda/content/document/cda.../9783319244310c2.pdf?SGWID
- <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/13664530300200184>